

RECRYSTALLISATION BEHAVIOUR IN A COLD DEFORMED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITE REINFORCED WITH ALUMINA PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Static recrystallisation behaviour has been investigated in an aluminium alloy (2014) matrix composite reinforced with ~20 volume percent aluminium-oxide particles and in a monolithic aluminium alloy (2014). Both materials were cold deformed to 30 percent reduction and annealed at various times and temperatures. Prior to deformation, both the composite and monolithic alloys were heat treated to the o-temper (fully stabilised microstructure). Recrystallization kinetics were monitored by hardness and electrical conductivity measurements. The microstructure was examined using optical microscopy. The composite was found to recrystallise faster than the unreinforced alloy and yielded a finer grain size which was highly stable.

Keywords: Composite; Metal Matrix; Particulate Reinforcement; Cold Work/Recrystallisation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites reinforced with large volume fractions of particles are now emerging as important structural materials because of their high modulus and strength [1,2]. These materials can be produced by a variety of methods such as molten metal mixing, spray deposition or powder metallurgy. Secondary fabrication usually involves conventional metal working processes such as extrusion, rolling or drawing. Parts can

be made using existing fabrication and machining techniques. The hot working of particulate reinforced metal matrix composites has been examined extensively (3,4,5) but studies of the microstructural development during cold deformation and subsequent annealing have been more limited (6,7,8). This work examines the recrystallisation behaviour and grain stability of an annealed Al-4% Cu alloy reinforced with Al_2O_3 particles.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The work was carried out on a commercial Al-4% Cu alloy, 2014, reinforced with approximately 20 volume % Al_2O_3 particles. The material was supplied by Alcan International Limited and had been produced by a molten metal mixing route and then cast and extruded as 9.5mm diameter bar. The recrystallisation behaviour of the composite was compared with that of an unreinforced (monolithic) 2014 aluminium alloy which had been direct chill cast, homogenised for 16 hours at 505°C then extruded to the same diameter as the composite. The composite and monolithic alloy were heat treated to produce a recrystallised grain structure. The heat treatment developed the O (annealed) condition with a fully stabilised CuAl_2 precipitate structure. It was necessary to compress the monolithic alloy 10% prior to heat treatment in order to recrystallise the original extruded grain structure.

Specimens 15mm long were cut from the heat treated rod and deformed in uniaxial compression at room temperature to a strain of 30%. The compression axis was parallel to the extrusion direction. After compression the specimens were stored at -10°C to minimise recovery. The specimens were then annealed in a fluidised bed furnace for one hour at temperatures ranging from 100 to 500°C. The recrystallisation kinetics were also examined in specimens isothermally annealed at 260°C, 360°C and 500°C for various times up to 100 hours. The specimens were quenched from the annealing temperature, and the hardness and electrical conductivity measured immediately to minimise any effects due to natural ageing or recovery. The hardness measurements were made on sections cut through the centre of the specimens perpendicular to the compression axis. Ten measurements were made on each specimen. The microstructure was examined using optical microscopy.

Measurements were also made of the volume fraction of the Al_2O_3 particles and their

Figure 1 Micrographs showing the (a) monolithic and (b) composite alloys.

Figure 2 Size distribution of Al_2O_3 particles.

Figure 3 Hardness as function of annealing temperature for the monolithic (2014-O) and composite (2014 MMC-O) alloys annealed for one hour after 30% cold compression.

size distribution. The volume fraction of the particles was determined from the weight change after dissolving the matrix material in a dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The particle size distribution was determined from the extracted particles using a Malvern 2600 size analyser.

3. RESULTS

Material characteristics

Micrographs of the monolithic and composite alloys after the initial heat treatment to the O condition are shown in Figure 1. Both alloys contain CuAl_2 precipitates of a similar size and distribution with the composite additionally containing the larger Al_2O_3 particles. The volume fraction of the Al_2O_3 particles was 22% and the mean particle size was $22\mu\text{m}$. The size distribution of the Al_2O_3 particles is shown in Figure 2.

Recrystallisation behaviour

The hardness is shown as a function of annealing temperature for the two alloys after a one hour anneal in Figure 3. The composite softened at a lower temperature than the monolithic alloy to give a recrystallisation temperature (midpoint in the hardness drop) about 50°C lower. A similar trend was observed from the conductivity measurements. The results of the isothermal annealing treatments are shown in Figure 4. At all three temperatures the composite recrystallised earlier than the monolithic alloy.

Recrystallised grain stability

The microstructure of the composite and monolithic alloy after annealing for 200 hours at 500°C are shown in Figure 5. The grain size of the composite after this extended recrystallisation treatment was $15\mu\text{m}$ compared with a value of $60\mu\text{m}$ for the monolithic alloy.

4. DISCUSSION

Large non-deformable particles, such as the Al_2O_3 particles in the composite, are known to accelerate recrystallisation by enhancing nucleation [3,4]. This effect, known as particle stimulated nucleation, has its origin in the prior deformation process. During cold working, highly misoriented deformation zones develop around the particles, due to the incompatibility between the plastically deforming matrix and the non-deforming particles, and these provide sites for early nucleation of recrystallised grains. In contrast, closely spaced fine particles inhibit recrystallisation since they homogenise the deformation process and restrict boundary mobility. When both coarse and fine particles are present together, as in the composite which contained fine CuAl_2 precipitates as well as the coarse Al_2O_3 particles, either acceleration or retardation can

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 Hardness as a function of annealing time for the (a) monolithic and (b) composite alloys.

Figure 5 Micrographs of the recrystallised grain structure in the (a) monolithic and (b) composite alloys.

Figure 6 Micrograph showing exaggerated subgrain growth adjacent to an Al_2O_3 particle during annealing.

occur. The present results clearly show that for the 2014 composite in the O condition recrystallisation is accelerated. Confirmation of the role of the Al_2O_3 particles in the process was obtained from the frequent observation of exaggerated subgrain growth at the particles, i.e. particle stimulated nucleation, as shown in Figure 6.

When particle stimulated nucleation occurs, a finer grain size results as seen in the present work. The mixture of Al_2O_3 particles and precipitates has inhibited grain growth, stabilising the fine recrystallised structure.

5. CONCLUSION

The results show that 2014 aluminium alloy in the O (annealed) condition reinforced with 20 volume % of coarse Al_2O_3 particles recrystallises faster than an unreinforced alloy, and yields a finer grain size which is highly stable. These findings are consistent with current views on particle stimulated nucleation.

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